

PROCESS PARAMETER STUDIES AND COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT PREFORM PROCESSES WITH NCF MATERIAL

F. Härtel^{1*}, P. Middendorf¹

¹ Institute of Aircraft Design, University of Stuttgart, Germany

* Frank Härtel (haertel@ifb.uni-stuttgart.de)

Keywords: *forming parameter study, test rig, quality control, NCF*

1 General Introduction

In recent years, a new wave of activities in research regarding complex forming of textile materials can be observed. Coming from the automotive sector, where people with a different background than the aerospace industry, urge to produce very complex shaped parts in CFRP.

One can criticize this approach and object it as black metal. However, it obliges to build up the capability to argue about possible and impossible forming processes and geometries.

Forming as a general term for 2D to 3D conversion of flat fabrics includes different processes like Laying, Folding and Draping. As Laying [1] and Folding [2] are very highly automated and use a manifold of different NCF products, Draping is not automated at all. In Draping processes the material class used most often is woven fabric. As they deform mainly in shear mode and this mode of deformation is understood very precisely by simulation and practice, they were the preferred material in the past. This can be followed also by the multitude of literature for woven fabrics, where just a small selection is listed [3-5]. Non-Crimp Fabrics are however an interesting material for Draping applications concerning their price and component performance. Major drawback is the more complex mode of deformation and therefore the lack of understanding for the actual internal processes in practice and simulation. Standard simulation models cannot account for the complex deformation modes existing in NCF material. More complex mesoscopic material models will be developed. The results of this work will be used for further improvement of these models. Only a small number of literary references exist and it underlines the idea of a non-solved challenge [6 - 8]. Where in woven fabrics one major mode of deformation can be found, there are

Figure 1: NCF Main Deformation Modes

three, often coupled ones, in a NCF forming process, see Fig. 1.

Especially Bel et al. [9] discuss the relevance of the changed deformation mode with NCF and give a direct comparison of the two fabrics in their paper.

In literature, it is often suggested to use deep drawing processes and blank holder as they are the most forward way to enable fiber slippage respectively fiber shearing in a material [10, 11]. Beside these obvious approaches, little work can be found regarding the comparison and optimization of forming processes of NCF material. Having noticed the lack of open accessible process knowledge, this paper was developed. By using simple truncated pyramid geometry and a well-defined material, the influence of process parameters and process modifications will be inspected.

Some pull-out experiments were conducted in advance in order to find reasonable material limitations and process information. A two-step approach was chosen with a set of initial experiments without any adaptation and a second set with optimized experiments.

There are different kinds of processes discussed and used in the preforming of textiles. A short overview

PROCESS PARAMETER STUDIES AND COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT PREFORM PROCESSES WITH NCF MATERIAL

can be seen in Fig.2. The ones which are examined in detail are marked in dark grey color.

Figure 2: CFRP forming process overview

Each process has its pros and cons, however, many of them can be reduced to the question of quality and automation potential, whereby in general the question of quality is much harder to discuss than the question of automation potential. High automation potential can be found where a small number of easy process steps can be used for the generation of preforms. This need however is in opposition to very complex parts.

The question of quality is more complex due to its direct dependency to the performance specification. The work presented here uses basic measurable parameters like deviation angle, extension of fiber waviness, out-of plane folds to evaluate the abilities to form NCF material.

The work concentrates onto a single easy geometry as the truncated pyramid has one well defined problem, which can be found in the corners. Each corner line represents a local double curvature for the material.

Fiber Slippage is the main deformation mechanism exploited here. The capability of the processes to generate this local fiber slippage in a very reproducible way is the key to a good forming result.

2 Material characterizations

The material used during the experiments presented in this paper was a unidirectional sewed carbon NCF, made by Saertex.

Figure 3: Geometrical Analysis of the truncated pyramid

Table 1: Material specification [11]

Manufacturer	SAERTEX GmbH & Co. KG	
Product	Unidirectional carbon fabric PB S32CU970-00320-02000-088939	
<i>Upper side</i>		
0°	Toray T620 50C	312 g/m ²
90°	E-Glass 34 tex	9 g/m ²
Binder	Momentive EPR 05390	8 g/m ²
<i>Lower side</i>		
Stitch Yarn	PES	6 g/m ²
Areal weight dry fabric		333 g/m ²
Areal weight powder		8 g/m ²

This material is a rather unique unidirectional fabric. It has a good handling behavior. One can easily handle it around, without provoking any defects. Nevertheless, it has very good drape ability. The fiber slippage is very reproducible and by this reproducible fiber slippage, the material behaves in total very reproducible during forming. This is not given in every case using different multi-axial NCF materials.

Most often unidirectional materials cannot perform well on both parameters, because of the high anisotropy in the material the material has to be heavily stabilized in the 90° direction in order to reach a good handling ability. This stabilization leads in the same moment to a poor formability due to blocked fiber slippage and rotation.

The chosen material has a loosely laid glass fiber on the back side, which is used for the sewing. A fiber

expansion in the cross direction is therefore possible up to 15%, but only with significant transversal force (good handling ability). The thread tension of the sewing seems to be chosen in a way, that fiber slippage is not hindered by too much compression of the sewing yarns. Therefore the fiber slippage is possible with a reasonable force level.

2.1 Material Test Rig

In order to investigate the limitation of the unidirectional material, some standard material tests have to be performed. The two process limitations needed are the breakout force for the occurrence of fiber slippage and the maximum transversal force, which does not harm the material integrity. Basically these two parameters could be found on a random textile testing machine. As at the Institute of Aircraft Design and Institute of Textile Technology and Process Engineering a new kind of basic material tester was developed, which is able to perform multi-axial loading on dry standard material specimens. The tests were performed on this testing machinery.

Figure 4: Material Test Rig

2.2 Material Limitation

2.2.1 Maximum Transversal Tension

The maximum transversal Force is the point were first significant material damage, like extensive gapping or breakage of the glass fiber direction occurs. The results are normalized to the number of glass roving.

Table 2: Maximum transversal Force for unidirectional carbon fabric

Number of trials	9
Minimum Force	10,4 N
Maximum Force	11,2 N
Mean Force	11 N
Standard Deviation	0,88 N

2.2.2 Breakout and Extraction Force

Figure 5: An Example for a Force-Displacement Curve of an Extraction Test under 8N/glass roving

The force level at which fiber slippage between two fibers starts to develop is important for the following experiments. After this breakout force a “constant” extraction force should settle (region up to 10mm), this is not the case with presented data due to collapse of the specimen at higher drag distances. Process forces which should lead to significant fiber slippage have to be above these forces. The breakout force is significantly depending on the transversal fiber tension. When the sewing thread is loaded with a transversal tension the friction forces which have to be overcome are much higher than without transversal loading. As the maximum transversal tension is known by the experiments conducted before, three discrete transversal points are chosen for examination of the break out force: 0N/glass roving, 4N/glass roving, 8N/glass roving.

Figure 6: Break out and Extraction Force under transversal loading

3 Process Characterizations

3.1 Process Test Rig

Comparable results or process parameters can only be generated if the processes are established in a comparable test environment and as many influencing parameters can be excluded or kept the same (geometry, thermal condition, reproducible positioning ...).

A multi-functional test rig was developed [14] at the Institute of Aircraft Design on which this study was performed. The test rig consists of two collaborating robots, eight electrical driven, force and position controlled actuators and thermal management for each material contact point and well defined fixation point all over the test rig.

Figure 7: Process Test Rig

3.2 Analyzed processes

The chosen processes are shown in Figure 2. A few details shall be given here:

3.2.1 Single diaphragm process

Figure 8: Diaphragm forming

A single diaphragm is placed on top of the flat laid specimen, then the geometry is pushed from underneath through the material and vacuum is applied.

Within a single diaphragm system the breakout force and the transversal fiber force is not easily controllable. As membrane forces affect all the area

beneath the diaphragm, all kind of fiber pre tensioning system is affected by membrane forces. A possible solution is the application of vacuum before penetrating the material in order to clamp the material or the standard blank holder system of the Punch and Die process.

3.2.2 Global Stamp

Figure 9: Global Stamp process

The material is placed on top of the geometry and a global stamp forms the material. Fibers can be set under pretension

In a global stamp system the fiber pre tensioning can be realized by spring or actuator constructions, which are rather complex compared to blank holder application.

3.2.3 Sequential Stamp

Figure 10: Sequential Stamp process

The material is placed on top of the geometry and a sequence of stamps form the material. Fibers can be set under pretension.

The advantage of a sequential process is the localization of different activities and their sequencing.

3.2.4 Punch-Die Forming

In the classic approach, a flat specimen is clamped by blank holders. A female geometry is placed on one side of the material,

and then a male stamp pushes the material into the geometry.

Figure 11: Punch and Die forming

Using a punch set-up where the punch penetrates a flat laying fabric blank holder is a simpler approach instead of complex pre-tensioning systems.

3.2.5 Secondary processes

In order to exclude the influence of secondary process parameters, standardization was chosen. Each specimen was cut to 400 x 400 mm. The specimen consists of two plies in the same orientation. Their binder side was set to the inside, in order to reach a sufficient stiffness for the following quality assurance procedure. This specimen was placed with an accuracy of +/- 1mm to the tooling, by the help of a laser projector. A tempered tool was used for binder activation. The tool was heated up to 120 °C, and then the process was started. After a tool temperature of about 75°C was reached, the quality assurance could be effectuated.

3.3 Quality control

The judgment of the quality is inherent to the judgment of the preforming process and is included in the test rig.

A robot based optical quality assurance system is working in the test rig. It is capable to detect forming errors in a three dimensional complex preform.

3.3.1 Quality definition

The term quality needs a strong definition with objective measurable parameters. In this work a combination of measurable draping effects will be taken into account. Folds, gaps, fiber deviation and fiber waviness are measured and then rated using the scheme of Table 3. Additionally the parameters will be weighted from one to four due to the magnitude of their consequences. As folds lead to a non process-able preform, its weighting factor is four.

Table 3: Quality Scheme for an objective quality definition

	Level						Weight
	1	2	3	4	5	6	
Folds (mm)	0	2	4	6	8	≥ 10	4
Gaps (mm)	0	1	2	3	4	≥ 5	2
Angle (deg)	0	2	5	10	15	≥ 20	2
Wavi. (-)	0	0,05	0,1	0,15	0,2	$\geq 0,25$	1

Gaps are initial starting points for failure and fiber deviation will diminish the mechanical performance significantly, therefore they are thought to be equally grave and are weighted with the factor of two. Fiber waviness will affect the mechanical properties but with lesser impact than the fiber angle deviation, the factor is chosen to one. The judgment scheme can be seen in Table 3.

Fiber waviness is taken as a quotient of the max. amplitude to its wavelength and therefore is dimensionless.

Figure 12: Example of an optical capture

Fiber deviation and waviness are taken from high resolution optical capture, see Figure . Gaps and Fold are identified using the thickness information of an optical topology measurement system. See Figure for an example.

Figure 13: Topology measurement (ATOS III)

4 Initial Experiments

4.1 Experimental design

In order to find an optimized process layout and to compare these optimized processes, a large number

of tests would be needed. In an attempt to limit the number of tests, the geometry was analyzed and segmented, see Figure 3. After the identification of critical areas, each process will be used with its standard parameter without any adaptation. The results will be analyzed and possible process optimization will be discussed.

The improved results will then be used to compare the processes to see the advantages and disadvantages of the processes.

The results of this work will also be used for the improvement of forming simulation. As described in a recent paper [14], standard forming simulation of NCF materials cannot sufficiently account for fiber slippage (which is stated to be a very important effect in NCF) and process influences. The data of this experimental work will be used to show the power of mesoscopic material models for forming simulation in a following paper.

4.1 Initial Experiments

During the initial experiments each process should be performed one time without any adaption, in order to examine in which degree the predicted problem areas, due to the geometrical feature, are affected by processes. The data of these initial experiments should be used to discuss the needed adaptations. Each process was carried out with 0° and 45° fiber orientation. For each process, an exemplary image was taken and the details are described in the text.

4.1.1 Single diaphragm process

Figure 14: Initial Experiment 0° - single diaphragm

The single diaphragm process had an average performance for both 0° and 45° orientations. Due to the “smooth” forming, only little fiber deviation and gapping were produced. As the “free” movement of

the fibers was not controlled, folds occurred quite heavily and in 45° direction fiber waviness was found to a larger extent.

An additional challenge of the diaphragm is the bridging effect in concave radii, which occurred during the initial trials in the marked regions.

As adaptation to the initial trails, the free movement of the fibers in the corner region has to be controlled. This can be done by using a combination of punch and die forming, where the die is the diaphragm. The material can be limited in the free movement by application of vacuum before the forming process or using the blank holder system of the punch and die forming process. The latter adaptation was used in the optimized set up. Using the acquired data from the preliminary tests, the minimal blank holder force F_N was found using the standard friction calculation:

$$F_{Pre} = \mu_S \times F_N \quad (1)$$

In fiber direction a normal force of about 160 N was applied in the corner region. In the cross direction a force of about 100 N was applied onto the whole side of the geometry.

4.1.2 Global stamp process

Figure 15: Initial Experiment 0° - global stamp

The global stamp process performed as expected in the initial 0° test, however in 45° direction many folds occurred. The results of the 0° test showed large folds. These folds are in a well-defined area of the outlet of the corners.

In order to enhance these results, the material has to be clamped and pre-tensioned at least in the fiber direction. To gain even more control, a clamping and pre-tensioning in the cross direction is

PROCESS PARAMETER STUDIES AND COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT PREFORM PROCESSES WITH NCF MATERIAL

advisable. The data gained in the material testing was used for the pre-tensioning. A force of about 4N/ glass roving was applied onto the cross direction and a force of about 50 N was used to provoke the fiber slippage.

4.1.3 Sequential stamp process

The sequential stamp process performed exactly as the global stamp process. Therefore it was concluded that single feature geometry could not show any significant difference between these two processes. As a result the sequential stamp was not pursued further. Nevertheless, for more complex geometries, with multiple cross-related features, global stamping is not possible any more. A sequential stamping process has to be used in these cases.

Figure 16: Initial Experiment 45° - Sequential Stamp

4.1.4 Punch and die forming

Figure 17: Initial Experiment 0° - Punch-Die

The punch and die process did not perform well in 0° direction. However, it was the best process for 45° regarding gapping, folds and fiber deviation. As the punch and die forming can be adapted easily using blank holder, a much better performance can be expected when the fibers are controlled tightly,

using the exactly same values for the normal forces from the diaphragm process.

4.1.5 Comparison of initial experiments

The processes performed behave quite similar (Fig. 18). The geometry is a simple one, which is the main reason for a very comparable behavior of the processes. Nevertheless, some first aspects regarding process comparison and general aspects can be listed:

Figure 18: Initial Process Comparison – Overview

Figure 19: Initial Process Comparison - detailed quality level for 0° and 45° orientation

PROCESS PARAMETER STUDIES AND COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT PREFORM PROCESSES WITH NCF MATERIAL

- 45° forming results in more distributed error regions (Fig. 18). Gapping is no problem, as fibers are always hold by an edge (Fig. 19).
- Without a thorough control of free fiber movement, no satisfying forming result can be obtained at all. Although the mean value does not seem too bad. The forming result is very poor, regarding folding. (Fig. 19)
- The Punch and Die process leads to the largest fiber waviness and gapping. It seems to be rather demanding process. (Fig. 19)
- Fiber deviation is significant and seems to be just slightly influence able (Fig. 19)

5 Process Comparisons

Using the given adaptation, the processes will be repeated three times for forming the truncated pyramid. These results can be used for a detailed comparison of the influence of the processes onto the forming defects and the reproducibility.

5.1.1 Single diaphragm process

Figure 20: Minor Fiber deviation ($<5^\circ$) in the 45° ply (upper picture), local fiber deviation at the corners (middle picture) and the 0° forming result without any folds (lower picture)

The forming result of the adapted diaphragm process is fold free.

Minor fiber deviations occur, but they are of a lower magnitude than in the initial trials. Where in the initial 45° trial, fiber angle deviation of about 10° could be found in Area 2-4, the deviation was lowered to about 2°. In the 0° trial, the same decrease in fiber deviation was realized. A minor fiber deviation of about 2-4° was still found in the outlet of the corner regions in both trials.

Small Fiber Waviness ($\sim 0,07$) could be found at the bottom point of the corner and no gapping at all.

5.1.2 Global Stamp process

Figure 21: Major Fiber deviation ($\sim 10^\circ$) in the 45° ply (upper picture), local fiber deviation in the corner (middle picture) and the 0° forming result with minor folds (lower picture)

PROCESS PARAMETER STUDIES AND COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT PREFORM PROCESSES WITH NCF MATERIAL

The forming result of the truncated pyramid and the directly neighboring areas are fold free. In the clamping region however some folds occur.

Significant fiber deviation can be found. They are of the same magnitude than in the initial trials and larger than with diaphragm and Punch and Die forming. A deviation of up to 30° can be found in Area 2 and 4 in the 0° trial and a deviation of up to 10° in the 45° trial.

Fiber Waviness could be found in the corners, orthogonal to the fiber direction (~0,1) in the 45° trial.

Besides the fiber deviation, gapping is a major problem in the 0° global stamp forming. As the load vector of the fibers has a transversal component in the flange areas significant gapping occurs here. With a lower load this gapping can be reduced slightly. Nevertheless this approach leads to non-perfect results or a very complex kinematic system as the load vector has to be perfectly aligned with the fiber direction at all time.

5.1.3 Punch and Die Process

The adaptation of the Punch and Die process worked fine. The introduced blank holder led to a fold free preform.

The fiber angle deviation in the 45° ply is larger than with the diaphragm process. A maximum deviation of about 13° was found, which is still better than in the initial trials. The largest part in Area 2-4 in the 0° ply is perfectly aligned, just the corner region is a little larger and with a higher deviation than in the diaphragm trial. The outlet of the corner in fiber direction has a fiber deviation of max. 1°. However, with the Punch and Die process the cross direction of the corner has a significant fiber deviation of about 15°, which is more local and pronounced than with the diaphragm process.

Small fiber waviness of about 0,1 and little gapping of about 2mm was found at the corner bottom point.

Figure 22: Significant Fiber deviation (<math><15^\circ</math>) in the 45° ply (upper picture), local fiber deviation at the corners (middle picture) and the 0° forming result without any folds (lower picture)

5.1.4 Process Comparison

Figure 23: Final Process Comparison - Overview

PROCESS PARAMETER STUDIES AND COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT PREFORM PROCESSES WITH NCF MATERIAL

Figure 24: Final Process Comparison - detailed quality level

When looking at the final results some clear tendencies can be found:

- Diaphragm behaves smoother in the forming compared to the other two processes. There are no “discrete” steps and therefore a smaller fiber deviation. (Fig. 24)
- All processes are adaptable using blank holder or pre-tensioning systems. These adapted process have no or at least less problems with fiber waviness and folds (Fig. 24)
- The adaptation of the global stamp process is the most complex one, as the perfect alignment of the pre tensioning system with the fiber direction is not easily guaranteed. If this is not fulfilled perfectly gapping occurs. (Fig. 23/24)
- Diaphragm forming produces little folds in the 45° ply, as maybe membrane forces can be adapted for even smoother forming, this might be suppressed. (Fig. 24)

- The Punch and Die process produced less folds and gapping during the comparison, however larger fiber deviation could be found (Fig. 24)

When forming more complex parts the author believes a combination of the three processes can lead to a successful forming. As Diaphragm forming leads to the least fiber deviation and Punch and Die forming to the least folding, these two processes seem to cooperate quite nicely. As local blank holders are needed in order to steer the fiber slippage, this task can be performed by sequential stamps, if the geometry is complex enough.

7 Conclusions and Outlook

In this paper, possible forming processes for NCF materials were evaluated experimentally and compared concerning their results in forming truncated pyramid geometries. Process limitations were shown and possible adaptation for an enhanced forming result provided. It was shown that simple material test could provide very helpful data for this optimization. Further steps will be to provide these data to mesoscopic material simulation in order to enhance the simulation model in an attempt to reach a prediction ability of the simulation. Further on, the investigation will be extended to more complex geometries. A combination of the different processes seems promising.

Acknowledgments

This project is funded by the European Union through the program “European Funds for Regional Development” as well as the federal state government of Baden-Wuerttemberg in Germany. Administrative agency of this program is the Ministry of Rural Development, Food and Consumer Protection. For more information visit

www.rwb-efre.baden-wuerttemberg.de.

References

- [1] K. Croft, L. Lessard, D. Pasini, M. Hojjati, J. Chenb, A. Yousefpour, Experimental study of the effect of automated fiber placement induced defects on performance of composite laminates, Composites: Part A 42 (2011) 484–491

- [2] Dr. J. Brandt, A. Geßler, J. Filsinger, New approaches in textile and impregnation technologies for the cost effective manufacturing of cfrp aerospace components, ICAS 2002
- [3] P. Boisse, N. Hamila, F. Helenon, B. Hagege , J. Cao, Different approaches for woven composite reinforcement forming simulation, ESAFORM - International Journal of Material Forming Volume 1, Number 1 / March 2008
- [4] S.G. Hancock, K.D. Potter, The use of kinematic drape modelling to inform the hand lay-up of complex composite components using woven reinforcements, Composites: Part A 37 (2006) 413–422
- [5] U. Mohammed, C. Lekakou, M.G. Bader , Experimental studies and analysis of the draping of woven fabrics, Composites: Part A 31 (2000) 1409–1420
- [6] M. Strauf Amabile, V. Eckers und T. Gries, Draping of Non-Crimp Fabrics for Fibre Reinforced Composites, ESAFORM - International Journal of Material Forming; 2010, Volume 3, Supplement 1
- [7] R.H.W. ten Thijsse, R. Loendersloot, R. Akkerman, Drape simulation of non-crimp fabrics, FALCOM project; 2003
- [8] S. Bel, P. Boisse, F. Dumont, Analysis of the deformation Mechanisms of Non-Crimp Fabric Composite Reinforcements during Preforming, Appl Compos Mater (2012) 19:513–528
- [9] Yu, W.R., Harrison, P., Long, A.C.: Ideal forming of non-crimp fabric performs through optimization of blank shape and blank holding force, Proc. Of 7th Esaform, 28th-30th April, Trondheim, Norway, 309–312 (2004)
- [10] Lee, J.S., Hong, S.J., Yu, W.-R., Kang, T.J.: The effect of blank holder force on the stamp forming behaviour of non-crimp fabric with a chain stitch. Compos. Sci. Technol. 67, 357–366 (2007)
- [11] Saertex GmbH, Inspection Certificate, SC32CU970-00320-02000-088939, Del. Note: 4041103, 21.08.2012
- [12] A.C. Long “Composite Forming Technologies”, 1st edition, Woodhead Publishing Limited, 2007
- [13] F. Härtel, P. Middendorf, A multifunctional Test Rig; Aachen-Dresdner Textiltagung; 2012
- [14] P. Böhler, F. Härtel, P. Middendorf, Identification of forming limits for unidirectional carbon textiles in reality and mesoscopic simulation; Key Engineering Materials Vols. 554-557 (2013) pp 423-432